

The impact of natural disturbances on the physical, chemical, and biological properties of forest soils: an umbrella review protocol

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Background

Anthropogenic climate change has increased the likelihood of extreme weather events such as droughts and storms. As a consequence of these changes in climate, the frequency and severity of other perturbations to forests such as fire (1), insect pest outbreaks (2), and plant pathogen outbreaks have also increased (3). These perturbations can increase tree mortality, altering carbon inputs to soils (e.g. leaf litter and coarse woody debris), and the abundance and diversity of soil dwelling organisms (4–6), all of which can potentially alter soil physical and chemical properties and, in turn, soil ecosystem functioning. Understanding the impacts of altered disturbance regimes on forest soil properties is vitally important in order to understand (i) wider threats to forest health, (ii) when managers should intervene to help soils recover, and (iii) feedbacks between different soil properties at multiple scales (7).

Much is already known about how different disturbances impact forest soil properties. Indeed, there have been a large number of quantitative evidence syntheses that attempt to address the impacts of different natural disturbances on the soil properties in forests (4–6, 8, 9). However the proliferation of meta-analyses in ecology (10, 11) means that it is now difficult to keep up-to-date with literature reviews, let alone the primary literature. In addition, individual syntheses of primary studies of the impacts of disturbance on soils are necessarily limited in scope, often focussing on single disturbances and/or single soil properties. For example, there have been multiple syntheses of the impacts of fire on different aspects of

soils, such as their effects on soil microorganisms (4, 6, 12), soil fauna (6, 13), soil nitrogen (12, 14–17), soil carbon (16, 17), and aggregate stability (18). However, there appears to have been relatively little synthesis of the impacts of some natural disturbances, such as those relating to insect herbivores (9), potentially constituting a knowledge gap. Another consequence of the increasing number of evidence syntheses is that there are often multiple different syntheses that address the impacts of a particular disturbance on a given soil property (e.g. the impact of fire on soil nitrogen (12, 14–17)). This makes it difficult to determine which synthesis should be used or why results might vary between seemingly identical studies - potentially leading to mistrust of meta-analyses (19) or evidence being ignored, despite the power of evidence synthesis to enable generalisations. Taken together this means that it is difficult for researchers and managers to access up-to-date information on the impacts of different disturbances on multiple soil properties and even when this is available, when there are multiple existing syntheses, it may be difficult to determine which source of evidence to use.

The problems associated with the sheer quantity of evidence syntheses are compounded by variation in their quality and therefore trustworthiness. In ecology the robustness of evidence syntheses appears to be low compared to other fields (20–22). A consequence of this is that if researchers and other stakeholders use the results of evidence syntheses without first appraising the quality of the study, as often likely happens, then they will be unaware that many of the studies are likely to misrepresent the impacts of disturbances (23).

Review objectives

In order to gain an overview of this topic, we will undertake an umbrella review of the impacts of natural disturbances on soil properties. We have six aims as part of this:

1. Summarise the mean effect sizes reported by existing quantitative syntheses, providing a broad overview of the impact of natural disturbances on soil physical, chemical, and biological properties of natural terrestrial ecosystems.
2. Quantify the between-study heterogeneity for each mean effect size, in order to determine their reliability.
3. Identify differences in the reported mean effect sizes of different quantitative syntheses and explore reasons for these differences.
4. Identify analyses that explore between-study heterogeneity and summarise these findings.
5. Assess the reliability of existing syntheses by critically appraising their methodologies.
6. Identify evidence synthesis gaps that constitute priorities for future synthesis.

Question components

We are interested in collating evidence from quantitative evidence syntheses that have assessed the impacts of natural disturbances on soil physical, chemical, and biological properties in forest ecosystems that are based on empirical measurements. As such, we have defined five important elements that guide the scope of our umbrella review: Population, Exposure, Comparison, Outcomes, (PECO) and Study type.

Population: We will include studies of soil physical, chemical, and biological properties in forest ecosystems. As such, we are not interested in studies that purely focus on croplands,

or on freshwater or marine ecosystems. We will include studies of forests in any biome, including boreal, temperate, and tropical zones.

Exposure: We are interested in studies that have investigated the impacts of different natural disturbances. The disturbances we are interested in include drought/reductions in precipitation, increases in rainfall, insect pests, plant pathogens, fire, and windthrow. For the purposes of this study we will not place any threshold on the intensity of disturbance that needs to be met to allow inclusion. As such, if a study reports that it studied the impacts of drought, or any of the disturbances we consider to be relevant exposures, we will consider it to be relevant under this criterion.

Comparison: We are interested in quantitative syntheses that are based on comparisons between sites that vary in the frequency or intensity of disturbance that they are subject to. These comparisons may include a control treatment vs. one or more treatments where type and/or level of disturbance are manipulated. This comparison may be spatial or temporal.

Outcomes: We are interested in any outcomes relating to the biological, chemical, and physical properties of soils. As such we will not predefine the precise outcomes in this protocol.

Study type: We will include only studies that have undertaken a quantitative synthesis of multiple, empirical primary studies.

Methods

Our study will consist of an umbrella review (24). This type of review aims to systematically compile evidence and synthesise information from multiple reviews into one document (25). The approach allows for a broad overview of a topic and is particularly useful when there are multiple outcomes and/or interventions/exposures of interest. They are also useful for highlighting when different syntheses on the same topic produce contradictory results, and potentially allow exploration for why this is the case. Outputs from umbrella reviews typically include: (i) a quantitative assessment of the impacts of multiple interventions/exposures on multiple outcomes; (ii) an assessment of the quality of existing evidence syntheses on a topic; and (iii) identification of gaps for future research synthesis.

At present we are unaware of standards and guidelines for umbrella reviews in the environmental sciences so we have adapted the existing Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) guidelines for umbrella review protocols in medicine for our needs (26). We combined these guidelines with those for syntheses in environmental management where we deemed necessary (27). In Table 1 we provide detail on which aspects of the JBI guidelines we followed and where we modified these.

Our review will also include some of the suggestions for compilation of 'evidence maps' in the environmental sciences, which comprise an assessment of the evidence provided by existing syntheses (28, 29). Throughout the sections relating to manual screening and data extraction, the protocol follows the reporting standards for systematic evidence syntheses in environmental research (ROSES) and the standards for systematic maps and reviews (30). During the development of this protocol we have undertaken regular scoping of different elements of the methodology to ensure that it is as clear and repeatable as possible as suggested by Foo et al (31)

Table 1 - Details of guidelines that we used to produce the umbrella review protocol. The abbreviations in the 'Source used' column are JBI: Joanna Briggs Institute Guidelines for Umbrella reviews (26); CEE: Collaboration on Environmental Evidence Guidelines and Standards for Evidence Synthesis in Environmental Management (27); and OL: Methods for evidence mapping, presented by O'Leary et al (28)

Guideline aspect	Source used	Guidelines followed	Alterations made and rationale
Title and author information	JBI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The title contains the phrase 'an umbrella review protocol' • There is more than one author • The affiliations of all authors was included 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post-nominal qualifications of authors were not included.
Developing the title and question	JBI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concise descriptive title 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A PECO question structure was used rather than a PICO structure because we are not investigating the impact of an intervention.
Background	JBI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive background section that covers all the main elements of the topic under review. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No search was undertaken for umbrella reviews on the topic, because preliminary searches suggested that there have been no umbrella reviews on ecological topics. • Vancouver style of referencing not used in order to make protocol more concise.
Review question or objective	JBI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The review questions are clearly stated 	None
Stakeholder engagement	CEE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We engaged with relevant stakeholders to ensure that inputs and outputs are of the greatest relevance and reliability to all interested parties. 	None
Eligibility screening	JBI and CEE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eligibility criteria are precisely defined (JBI) • Type of population is clearly defined (CEE) • Type of exposure is clearly defined (CEE) • Type of relevant study is clearly defined (JBI) • Eligibility criteria are provided for all stages of screening (CEE) • Eligibility criteria will be independently applied by more than one reviewer (CEE) • Consistency of screening decisions between reviewers will be measured and reported (CEE) • The number of unique articles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The type of outcome considered relevant is broadly defined, but since we are looking for multiple outcomes for soil properties we cannot define this in detail.

		<p>found during the search and excluded at each stage will be fully reported (CEE)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The reasons for exclusion of each article considered at the full text screening stage will be given (CEE) • A list of articles which have unclear eligibility status will be reported (CEE) • A list of all studies included in the final review will be reported (CEE) 	
Search strategy	JBI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Our search aims to identify all research syntheses relevant to the review question. • We will search for grey literature using Google Scholar. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extended search to include studies prior to 1990. • Searched databases relevant to ecology rather than medical databases, due to the focus of our study.
Assessment of methodological quality	JBI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All syntheses will be critically appraised. • Critical appraisal will be done by two independent reviewers. • Comparisons between appraisal by different reviews will be made and where there is lack of consensus reviewers will discuss reasons for this. • We will define an a priori quality threshold that syntheses must meet to be included in the umbrella review. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rather than using the JBI critical appraisal tool we will use the CEESAT tool, since it was developed specifically for syntheses in the environmental sciences.
Data collection	JBI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviewers will discuss and pilot the data extraction tool prior to extracting data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We will use a modified version of the JBI data extraction tool. • Rather than two reviewers extracting data for all studies, all reviewers will extract data from a random selection of 10% of syntheses. Once sufficient agreement is achieved, reviewers will extract data independently.
Data summary	JBI and OL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We will present a summary of existing research syntheses (JBI). • We will also present visualisations to characterise syntheses and identify evidence gaps (OL). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although JBI umbrella reviews do not aim to further synthesise results of publications, we will aim to carry out some further syntheses, such as identifying potential reasons for differences amongst similar synthesis studies.

Stakeholder engagement

The topic and research questions were developed as part of the HoliSoils project, which focuses on holistic management practices, modelling, and monitoring for European forest soils (<https://holisoils.eu/>). The topic was defined in a series of meetings with researchers who form the HoliSoils consortium and feedback via email on proposed topics. Following this, a series of questions were proposed and feedback from consortium members was included. In addition, we defined a review team (the authors of this protocol) which will guide the development of synthesis during the project.

Search procedure

Our search strategy is designed to retrieve publications that comprise quantitative syntheses on the impacts of the focal natural disturbances on soil properties in forest ecosystems. To do this we will search for publications in three bibliographic platforms: Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar. We will not restrict the search to articles during a particular period of time but will screen all papers produced by searches. The rationale for using multiple databases for our search is that using single bibliographic platforms can lead to studies being missed (23). In addition to formal searches, we will accept suggestions for suitable studies from stakeholders that may be interested in the review. We will contact expert researchers in the field to ask for suggestions of syntheses that might be relevant.

Table 2 - Search string components associated with different PECO elements. The search strings in this table represent the format used for searches in the Web of Science. Formats for other bibliography platforms are given in Supplementary file 1.

PECO element	Search string component
Population	(soil* OR litter)
Exposure	(drought* OR *fire* OR burn* OR wind* OR typhoon* OR cyclone* OR *storm* OR "canopy gap*" OR rain* OR precipitation OR irrigat* OR disturb* OR "bark beetle*" OR pest OR "insect herbivore*" OR "insect infestation" OR "insect outbreak" OR "beetle outbreak" OR "pathogen*" OR "phytophthora*")
Comparison	None
Outcome	None
Study type	((synthes* NEAR/5 (evidence OR research OR quantitative)) OR "meta-analys*" OR "meta analys*" OR "systematic review")

We developed search terms that we will use for our umbrella review based on the different PECO elements of our questions and scoping of these terms using the Web of Science and Scopus platforms. We decided to restrict our search terms to those related to the population,

exposure, and study type elements because we were concerned that syntheses may not give details of the outcome and comparison elements in their titles or abstracts. In addition, we chose not to include search terms specific to forest ecosystems as many syntheses only present details of analyses related to particular ecosystem types in the full text of the article, not in the title or abstract. Once our search terms returned all our benchmark studies (see below) all references were downloaded and duplicates removed using the R package *synthesisr* (32). Table 2 gives details of the different keywords and associated PECO elements for this study.

Search languages

We will review publications in English only, and make a record of all publications that we excluded because they were not in English. We acknowledge that excluding literature written in non-English languages is a shortcoming that may lead to biases (33, 34), such as accentuating spatial biases towards temperate ecosystems. However, we lack the resources needed to work in other languages, especially since checking consistency of inclusion requires dual-screening of articles.

Assessment of search comprehensiveness

To estimate the comprehensiveness of our search the review team developed a benchmark list of quantitative syntheses that meet our inclusion criteria. These represent articles that we feel our searches must capture in order to be considered comprehensive - as recommended by guidelines for environmental evidence synthesis (27). Table 3 gives a summary of the benchmark studies.

Table 3 - Details of benchmark studies used to assess the comprehensiveness of our search strategy. For more detail see Supplementary file 1.

Reference	Disturbance(s)	Relevant outcome(s)
Pressler, Moore & Cotrufo (6)	Fire	Microbial biomass, microbial richness, microbial evenness, microbial diversity, fauna abundance
Zhou, Wang & Luo (5)	Decreased precipitation, increased precipitation	Microbial richness, microbial biomass, microbial respiration, net N mineralization rate, nitrification activity, denitrification activity, enzyme activity.
Kristensen, Rousk & Metcalfe (9)	Insect pests	Bacterial abundance, fungal abundance, root biomass, carbon turnover, ammonification, nitrification, phosphorus turnover, soil C, soil N, C leaching, N leaching
Wan et al (14)	Fire	Soil N, soil ammonium, soil nitrate
Wang et al (12)	Fire	Soil organic carbon, Soil N, Soil N mineralisation
Holden and Tresseder	Fire, storm, insect pests	Total microbial biomass, Fungal, biomass, bacterial biomass

(35)		
Homyak et al (36)	Drought	Soil microbial biomass, N mineralisation, ammonia, ammonium, nitrous oxide emissions
Vasconcelos et al (13)	Fire	Ant abundance and diversity
Liu et al (37)	Drought, precipitation increases	Soil moisture, soil temperature, soil respiration
Zhou et al (38)	Drought, precipitation increases	Soil carbon, Microbial carbon
Thom and Seidl (39)	Fire, windthrow, insect pests	Soil organic carbon
Song et al (40)	Drought, precipitation increases	Root biomass, soil respiration
Zhang et al (41)	Insect pests, plant pathogens	Root biomass, soil organic carbon, microbial biomass carbon, dissolved organic carbon, soil respiration
Johnson and Curtis (16)	Fire	Soil carbon, Soil nitrogen
Maynard et al (15)	Fire	Soil nitrogen, soil phosphorus, soil calcium, soil mercury,
Gao (42)	Drought	Soil nitrogen, soil phosphorus
Yan et al (43)	Drought, precipitation increases	CO ₂ flux, CH ₄ flux, and N ₂ O fluxes
Blankinship et al (44)	Drought, precipitation increases	Soil fauna, soil microorganisms
Nave et al (45)	Fire	Soil nitrogen, soil carbon

Platforms to be searched

Scopus and Web of Science searches will use the 'title, keyword, and abstract' and 'topic' functions respectively. We will search the Web of Science Core Collection but no other databases on the platform. We will also search the Scopus platform. In addition to specialist bibliographic platforms we will search one web-based search engine, Google Scholar. To assist this we will use the R package gsscraper to bulk download the first 100 relevant references found during searches of Google scholar. Previous work has shown that Google Scholar can be useful for finding both academic and grey literature (46).

All references will be downloaded as .bib or .ris files and the R package *synthesisr* used to remove duplicate articles (32). We will then import the full library into Zotero, which we will use to convert the references to an Endnote XML file. We will then upload this xml file to *sysrev* (47) - an online tool that allows for collaborative screening and data extraction by review teams. Using *sysrev* will allow the screening process to be as transparent as possible as it will allow people that are interested in the review to examine decisions about the inclusion/exclusion of studies.

Article Screening and Study eligibility criteria

Screening process

Articles will be screened using *sysrev* (47) using the eligibility criteria detailed below. First, titles and abstracts will be screened for relevance. Articles that meet inclusion criteria or that do not provide enough detail to determine whether they meet inclusion criteria at the title and abstract screening stage will be retained following which their full text will be reviewed.

Consistency checking

To check for consistency, a random sample of 10% of titles and abstracts will be screened by two team members, using our inclusion criteria. Any disagreements between the two people will be discussed, and eligibility criteria will be revised to show how disagreements were resolved. Kappa scores will be calculated to test the agreement between the two people (48). If Kappa scores are below 0.6, another 10% of titles and/or abstracts will be screened by the same two team members. Disagreements will be discussed and resolved again, Kappa scores recalculated, and the consistency checking process repeated until Kappa scores are greater than 0.6. Following this, a sample of 10% of the full texts of publications that meet inclusion criteria based on their titles/abstracts will be screened by two people. This process will mirror that detailed above for title/abstract screening. Kappa scores and percentage agreement at each round of the screening stage will be reported as part of the umbrella review. Members of the review team will not be allowed to make a decision about inclusion of an article that represents a conflict of interest. If review team members encounter an article on which they are a co-author or that is written by a close colleague, they will make a note of this conflict of interest and not review the study for inclusion.

Inclusion criteria

To meet our eligibility criteria studies must:

1. Be a quantitative synthesis of multiple primary studies in which an effect size is reported
2. Synthesise soil or litter biological, chemical, or physical properties
3. Address the impact of a focal exposure, either drought, increases in precipitation, wind, fire, insect herbivores, plant pathogens of interest on soil properties in forest ecosystems
4. Include studies that made comparisons between sites that vary in the intensity or frequency of the disturbance that they were exposed to
5. Calculate effect sizes to allow for comparisons
6. Be written in English

Figure 1 - Summary of the screening process to be used in this umbrella review

Our eligibility criteria will be applied at two stages: (i) title and abstract screening; and (ii) full-text screening. At the title and abstract screening stage, in order to be retained, articles must meet or possibly meet criteria 1-3. At the full-text stage criteria 1-5 must be met in order for an article to be retained. Abstract-level and full-text screening are summarised in Figure 1. At the full-text screening stage, we will provide a reason for the exclusion of all articles that do not meet our inclusion criteria in accordance with ROSES guidelines (30). Reasons may include the inability to find or access the full text of an article, an article not being written in English, or a lack of PECO elements (Figure 1).

Assessment of methodological quality

We will use umbrella review to assess and combine multiple syntheses about the impacts of different natural disturbances on multiple soil outcomes. This is in contrast to the relatively narrow approach typical of individual syntheses which usually focus on one or a small number of outcomes for one disturbance. While our approach allows broad questions to be addressed, one major problem with it is that the robustness of the results of an individual synthesis depends on the quality of the methodology of individual meta-analyses. This is a particular concern in ecology because the robustness of the methodology used in evidence syntheses is likely to be relatively low compared to other fields (20–22).

To limit the problems associated with varying robustness of syntheses, as part of our umbrella review we will perform a critical appraisal of the syntheses that meet our inclusion criteria, as recommended by the JBI guidelines for umbrella reviews (26). To do this we will use the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence Synthesis Appraisal Tool (CEESAT) checklist (20, 21). This checklist can be used to assess the objectivity, comprehensiveness, and transparency of the synthesis, and as a result it aids in determining the reliability of their results. This constitutes 16 questions relating to the quality of each meta-analysis which can be scored as ‘Gold’ (highest robustness), ‘Green’, ‘Amber’ or ‘Red’ (lowest robustness). In

order to provide an overall score for each synthesis we will classify a publication as the most commonly occurring classification. We will also produce a continuous score for each question between 0 ('Red') and 3 ('Gold'), to create a continuous variable for assessment of study robustness. The details of this scoring system are provided in the supplementary materials. To ensure repeatability of the scoring process at least 10% of relevant articles will be screened by two or more reviewers, following a process similar to that for study inclusion. All syntheses classified as 'Red' will be excluded from analyses that summarise the impacts of different disturbances on soil outcomes as well as any syntheses of heterogeneity.

Data coding and extraction

One quantitative synthesis commonly contains multiple types of meta-analysis. For example, they regularly report a 'global' meta-analysis which constitutes a meta-estimate of all studies that relate to a particular outcome. However, because quantitative syntheses in ecology often exhibit high between-study heterogeneity(49), they often also present subgroup analyses or metaregressions exploring how variables such as study methods, region, or ecosystem type alter effect sizes. As such, for our study we need to identify which of these analysis types is of most interest.

Our interest is in assessing the general impacts of different natural disturbances on the biological, chemical, and physical properties of soils in forest ecosystems. As such, we will extract data from analyses that present (i) meta-estimates of impacts on soil properties; (ii) exploration of heterogeneity for these impacts. This information will be extracted from tables, text, or figures along with data on the confidence intervals and sample size (number of studies and number of pairwise comparisons). To aid with interpretation of mean effect sizes we will extract the I^2 statistic (52), which reflects the percentage of variation in an effect size that is due to between-study variance. Values of 50% or less are considered to be low, 51-75% as medium and >75% as high. Higher I^2 values may indicate the need to explore heterogeneity in a meta-analysis. We expect most meta-analyses in our umbrella review to produce high I^2 values, since most meta-analyses in ecology have high between study heterogeneity (53). We provide more detail below on the exact nature of the data which we plan to extract.

We will extract information from each of the syntheses, adapted from (26). These variables will include:

- *Study details* - We will record standard bibliographic data about each publication such as the title, author, year, source of publication etc.
- *Objectives of synthesis* - For each synthesis we will state the general aim(s) of the study
- *Population(s) studied* - The population(s) studied in each synthesis. Where more than one population has been studied we will record details of all of these.
- *Disturbance(s) studied* -The disturbance(s) studied in each synthesis. Where more than one disturbance has been studied we will record details of all of these.
- *Outcome(s) studied* - The outcome(s) studied in each synthesis. Where more than one outcome has been studied we will record details of all of these.
- *Geographic scope of synthesis*- We will record whether syntheses had a global, regional, or national scope as well as including the regions/countries included in the study.
- *Ecosystem types studied* - The different types of forest ecosystems in which primary studies were undertaken, including boreal, temperate, mediterranean, and tropical.

- *Soil types included* - Did the synthesis include primary studies of mineral soils, organic soils, or both?
- *Search details* - The specific details of the search undertaken by the syntheses, where they are reported.
- *Sources searched* - We will record the names of the search platforms used to undertake the literature search for each synthesis, where they are reported.
- *Year range of studies included* - The years in which primary studies included in the synthesis were published.
- *Number of studies included* - The number of primary studies included in each of the synthesis studies.
- *Number of comparisons included* - The number of effect size estimates used for each synthesis.
- *Study designs included (e.g. before-and-after; randomised controlled study etc).* - The range of designs considered to be valid for each of the synthesis studies, where it is stated. If no statement is made regarding study designs we will consider that all types of study design have been included.
- *Scale of field studies* - The spatial scale of field studies included in syntheses, where it is stated.
- *Inclusion of field/greenhouse/lab studies* - Description of the type of primary studies included in the synthesis, where it is stated. If no statement is made regarding study types we will consider that all types of study have been included.
- *Summary of inclusion criteria* - A description of the criteria used to determine whether primary studies should be included in a synthesis study.
- *Rules used by syntheses for inclusion of multiple data points from studies* - A description of the rules used when there were multiple pairwise comparisons from syntheses. Ecological meta-analyses commonly include more than one effect size from a single primary study, either because of repeated measurements over time, or because of multiple comparisons with one control group.
- *Appraisal of primary studies* - Identification of whether syntheses appraise the risk-of-bias of primary studies.
- *Method of analysis* - In order to assess the validity of a study's analysis we will collect data on (i) what kind of meta-analytical model was used; (ii) whether and how publication bias was investigated.
- *Results of meta-analysis* - A narrative summary of the general findings for each outcome for each synthesis, excluding any sub-group or metaregression analyses.
- *Mean effect size* - the mean effect size relating to the impact of a focal disturbance on a focal soil outcome and relating to forest ecosystems.
- *Effect size variability* - a measure of variability around the mean effect size, such as the 95% confidence interval or standard error.
- *Sample size for mean effect size* - the number of articles and the number of comparisons used for calculation of each mean effect size.
- *Significance/direction* - A summary of the significance and direction of effects for each outcome for each synthesis.
- *I² statistic* - For each mean effect size we will extract the I² statistic, which reflects the percentage of variation in an effect size that is due to between-study variance.
- *Presence of heterogeneity analysis* - a record of whether a study conducted any analysis to explore between-study heterogeneity.

- *Type of heterogeneity analysis* - Identification of whether any heterogeneity analysis carried out represented a sub-group analysis, using a categorical variable, or a meta-regression, using a continuous variable.
- *Results of heterogeneity analysis* - A narrative summary of the general findings for each heterogeneity analysis undertaken in each synthesis
- *Sub-group categories* - Identification of the categories used for each sub-group analysis.
- *Sub-group means* - The means for each category in a sub-group analysis.
- *Sub-group variability* - The variability around the mean for each category in a sub-group analysis.
- *Meta-regression variable* - Description of the continuous variable used in meta-regression analyses.
- *Meta-regression variable units* - The units used for the continuous explanatory variable used in meta-regression analyses.
- *Meta-regression slope* - The slope of the meta-regression.
- *Meta-regression slope variability* - The variability around the estimate of the slope in the meta-regression analysis.
- *Data shared* - Flag to identify when the data used for analyses has been shared as supplementary materials or in a repository. This data will potentially be used in future synthesis work.

To ensure that data extraction is as repeatable as possible, we will use two reviewers to extract data from all studies. Any disagreements will be discussed and methods for data extraction will be modified where relevant. For all data extracted, we will also report the location of the study data within each article. We will make data extraction forms available in the supplementary material of the published manuscript.

Data synthesis

We will perform analyses to characterise the evidence we collate from previous syntheses. These analyses will include analysis of the populations, disturbances, and outcomes studied in syntheses; the geographic scope of syntheses; the types of ecosystem studied; the designs of primary studies included; an assessment of how up-to-date syntheses are; and an assessment of the risk-of-bias of each synthesis.

For each combination of disturbance and outcome for which we obtain suitable data we will quantitatively summarise results relating to the mean effect sizes reported in each synthesis. This summary will involve (i) plotting and reporting in a table the summary effect size for each synthesis along with corresponding confidence intervals and sample sizes; (ii) calculation of the between-study heterogeneity of each synthesis, using the I^2 metric, where possible. Following (49) where the I^2 metric is not reported in original studies, we will attempt to calculate it ourselves using the original primary study level data where it is supplied in synthesis studies. If we find a sufficient number of papers (approximately 10 or more) with similar focal exposures and outcomes we will explore the reasons for differences in mean effect sizes. Our a priori hypotheses about what causes differences between syntheses that investigate the same outcome for the same disturbance are:

1. The scope of syntheses is a primary driver of differences in mean effect size amongst similar syntheses. To test this we will use generalised linear models to test the impacts of the different forest types included in syntheses, the geographic scope of

studies, and whether they only included field studies or also included greenhouse studies.

2. The mean effect size of a synthesis is related to its methodological robustness. To test this we will use generalised linear models to investigate the impact of scores generated by CEESAT on the mean effect size of syntheses. The rationale for doing this is that it has previously been found that variation in the methodological robustness of literature searches can result in differences in mean effect sizes (23).
3. The mean effect size of a synthesis is related to the quantity of literature it summarises. We will test this using a generalised linear model to identify any relationship between the number of papers summarised by a synthesis and its mean effect size.

Due to the fact that there is likely to be a relatively small number of studies that share focal outcomes and exposures, the analyses detailed about will all be univariate in nature. We will compare between models using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), to choose the most parsimonious model.

To summarise heterogeneity analyses we will report results in a table and plot the results of subgroup analyses and meta-regressions in separate figures. We do not plan to carry out any analyses to explore reasons for differences in the results of heterogeneity analyses, although we will discuss this narratively. To identify potential knowledge gaps we will also draw on the ideas of O'Leary et al (28) by producing heatmaps and similar graphics to indicate which disturbances and which outcomes have been covered by existing syntheses, and how these syntheses vary in quality and recency.

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